

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Immunological and biochemical characterization of chitinase with protease activity against Rapither AB

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 OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Gupta A, Pawar M, Sharma S, Pendharkar N. Immunological and biochemical characterization of chitinase with protease activity against Rapither AB. *MicroMed.* 2017; 5(2): 37-44.

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.832439>

Received: May 22, 2017

Revised: July 18, 2017

Accepted: July 20, 2017

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Transparency declaration: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical considerations: All these studies were conducted under IBSC guidelines and approved by IBSC committee of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, India.

ABSTRACT

The objective of our study is to confirm and isolate the enzyme chitinase from bacterial samples that are present in different soil samples of Baramati region, Maharashtra and determined its antimicrobial activity of chitinase with protease activity against Rapither AB in virally infected human whole blood samples. In this study, soil samples of different regions of Baramati were collected and identified chitinase enzyme on the basis of zone inhibition in chitin agar plates and finally confirmation through Bergey manual method. For these studies, quantifying the protein content including crude enzyme of bacterial colonies using Nanodrop method. In addition, protease activity of chitinase crude enzyme was determined against Rapither AB and estimated its proliferation rate including total cellular content in virally infected human whole blood samples. After confirmation of chitinase enzyme through various biochemical tests (protein content) and showed higher or rich amount of protein including crude enzyme at a very low concentration. In contrast, protease at higher concentration showed declined in proliferation rate including total cellular content in virally infected human whole blood samples. Overall studies indicated its antimicrobial activity of chitinase with protease activity against Rapither AB.

Keywords: Chitinase; Protease; Rapither AB; Proliferation.

INTRODUCTION

Chitin (polymer of N-acetylglucosamine) is one of the main structural component of the cell wall of fungi. It is crystalline in structure and is generally observed as well as studied through X-ray diffraction technique [1]. This chitin is directly bound to polysaccharides including protein components as well. As per the literature, three forms of arrangement of chitin i.e. α , β and γ are reported [1, 2]. Normally, these chitin components does not able to accumulate in the environment because of the presence of various bacterial chitinases which are present abundantly especially in soil. These enzymes are one of the most reliable candidates that are responsible for degrading chitin molecules that are present in the cell walls of fungi as well as the exoskeletons of insect. One of the useful aspects of chitinase enzyme is for bioconversion of chitin into active pharmacological products especially N-acetylglucosamine and chitooligosaccharides [1-3]. These products are

generally required for various immunopharmacological activities (antioxidants, wound healing, antimicrobials, immunoenhancers etc.) and also activates host defense system including controlling the level of blood cholesterol [3-4].

Chitinases are widely distributed in bacteria such as *Serratia*, *Chromobacterium*, *Klebsiella*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *vibrio*, *Arthrobacter* etc. Number of bacterial species are reported and claimed as good source of bioactive compounds i.e. antibiotics, enzymes etc. The production of chitinolytic enzymes has been identified in various bacterial species [5, 6]. Now a day, scientists focused on chitinase enzymes for various industrial, clinical, and pharmaceutical purposes [5-8]. In this regard, we tried to explore the effect of protease extracted from chitinase enzyme containing Rapither AB.

One of the parasitic diseases especially Malaria is spread to people through the bites of infected female anopheles mosquitos. Till now, only four main strains of malaria are reported, out of these the most serious strain is falciparum. In comparison with other three strains (*vivax*, *ovale* and *malariae*) are less serious as compared to falciparum. But we still need to be prevented and treated promptly [9, 10]. In Asian and African countries, Malaria is considered as one of the major life threatening disease [11]. Recently, Rapither AB used as anti-malaria segment or used in the form of injection as medicine for the treatment of malaria and other conditions [12]. In this regard, we determined its protease activity of chitinase enzyme containing Rapither AB in virally infected human whole blood samples.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Microorganisms and culture conditions

In this study, we identified various bacterial (i.e. *Bacillus* species, *Pseudomonas* species, *Streptomyces* species etc.) samples that are reported in soil and showed high chitinase activity as mentioned in the literature. These bacterial species were identified as well as isolated in our lab from various soil samples (rhizosphere of pomogranate, jawar, ground and fish market) collected aseptically from different regions of Baramati, Maharashtra, India.

Colloidal chitin

For the preparation of colloidal chitin using concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl, 120 ml) and it was dissolved slowly in chitin powder (10 g). This sample was put in rotary incubator (180 rpm) at 37 °C for 1h. Filter the solution through glass wool/muslin cloth and then dissolved in equal quantity of ethanol (50%). Mix properly and then transfer through filter paper. Finally, add distilled water and then finally reached its final concentration with pH 7. Collect the samples and store at 4 °C. Finally, this solution was used for media preparation [13].

Colloidal chitin agar medium and purification of chitinase enzyme

For screening of chitinase producing bacteria, the agar medium amended with colloidal chitin was used. The medium consists of disodium hydrogen phosphate (6 g), potassium dihydrogen phosphate (3 g), ammonium chloride (1 g), sodium chloride (0.5 g), yeast extract (0.05 g), agar (15 g) and colloidal chitin (1%) dissolved in one litre of distilled water that are prepared aseptically. The confirmation of these bacterial colonies showing clearance zones on a creamish background and were considered as chitinase-producing bacteria [13].

After confirmation, inoculate chitinase producing colonies in colloidal chitin broth for 48 h rotatory incubation. Thereafter, centrifuging at 10,000 rpm for 20 min, supernatant was collected and then add ammonium sulfate in small quantity. Incubate these samples overnight at 4°C. Again, centrifuging the samples at the same speed, again collect the supernatant and undergoes dialysed for 24 h at 4°C with continuous stirring and occasional changes of the buffer. The resultant dialysate was chitinase crude extract.

Estimation of biochemical tests (protein content)

In this study, colonies of chitinase were collected and estimated the protein content. Colonies of chitinase were added in test tube and then add extraction buffer (i.e. 20 mM Tris HCl) dissolved in PBS (pH 7.4). Incubate chitinase colonies along with extraction buffer for 5 minutes at room temperature and then centrifuged (5500 rpm; 8 minutes at 4°C). Finally, the supernatant was collected after centrifugation and then add similar volume of ice cold acetone.

Incubate the solution for 10-15 minutes at room temperature and then centrifuging at the same speed. Thereafter, pellet was taken and washed with ice cold acetone in order to remove the pigments including lipid contents as well. Finally, protein concentration of chitinase colonies was determined by using Nanodrop method [14].

Estimation of protease content

After getting the protein from chitinase colonies that are dissolved in PBS. For crude enzyme collection, centrifuging the protein content (10000 rpm at 4°C for 30 minutes) and then estimate its crude enzyme and then measured its protease content against Rapither AB.

Calorimetric assay was performed for protease estimation using Rapither AB as substrate. For these studies, add equal volume of Rapither AB and crude enzyme extract of chitinase in 2 ml Eppendorf tube. Incubate the test solution for 2-3 h at room temperature. After incubation, trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solution was added in order to stop enzymatic reaction. Centrifuging these samples (crude enzyme containing Rapither AB) and supernatant was collected finally and then add similar volume of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution in comparison with trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solution. Incubate it another 20 minutes at room temperature. Thereafter, addition of Folin Colin reagent (0.5 ml) and the intensity of blue color was measured at 700 nm within half an hour using spectrophotometer [15].

Total cellular content

Infected EDTA human whole blood (virally infected) samples (n=5; 50 µl) were collected from Mangal laboratory (Pathology lab, Baramati) was pipetted directly into a eppendorf tube containing variable concentration of protease dissolved in PBS and then incubated at carbon dioxide incubator (37°C, 5% CO₂) for 2 h. After incubation, add red cell lysis buffer (ammonium chloride, potassium bicarbonate and ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid) and then centrifuged. Pellet was taken and washed 2-3 times with PBS. After washing, pellet (leucocytes) dissolved in PBS and studied total cellular content. All these samples were measured at 570 nm using UV spectrophotometer [14-15].

Proliferation assay

In this study, lysed infected human whole blood samples (100 µl) were added in 96 well plate (flat bottom tissue culture plate) and treated with variable concentration of protease isolated from chitinase, enzyme containing Rapither AB as antigen. For 24 h incubation at carbon dioxide incubator, lysed blood samples along with variable concentration of proteases dissolved in PBS containing 10% FBS (Fetal bovine serum). After incubation, add MTT solution (2.5 mg/ml; 10 µl; dissolved in PBS) and then incubated again at carbon dioxide incubator for 4 h. Afterwards, formazon crystals were appeared and settled at the bottom. These crystals were dissolved in DMSO (dimethyl sulphoxide) and then its optical density (OD) was measured at 570 nm [14-15].

Statistical analysis

Values are represented in the form of Mean ± standard error. The difference between the control and treated groups of proteases is determined by one way ANOVA test (Bonferroni multiple comparison test).

RESULTS

Estimation of protein and protease content

The results of these studies related to protein content including crude enzyme isolated from the chitinase-producing colonies as shown in Fig. 1 and 2. The results showed that chitinase-producing colonies showed lot of protein content at a very low concentration (10 µl containing 5.342 mg/ml) including crude enzyme (10 µl containing 79-85 mg/ml). In addition, crude enzyme of chitinase-producing colonies containing Rapither AB showed enormous production of protease i.e. 57.81 mg/ml (Fig. 3) as compared to Rapither AB (33.82 mg/ml).

Figure 1. Estimation of protein content from chitinase-producing colonies.

Figure 2. Estimation of crude enzyme extracted from protein content of chitinase-producing colonies.

Figure 3. Estimation of protease content from crude enzyme of chitinase colonies containing Rapither AB.

Figure 4. Estimation of total cellular content of protease extracted from chitinase colonies containing Rapither AB on virally infected human whole blood samples. Lysed virally infected human whole blood was cultured with variable doses of proteases. Values are expressed as Mean ± S.E. The difference between control and variable doses of medicinal plant products is controlled by one way ANOVA test (Bonferroni multiple comparison test). *P<0.05; **P<0.01.

Figure 5. Proliferation assay. Virally infected lysed human whole blood was cultured with variable concentration of proteases. After incubation, centrifuge the samples and add MTT solution (5 mg/ml, 10 µl). Fresh formazan crystals were appeared and settled at the bottom and then finally dissolved in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) in a final volume of 0.2 ml. The optical density (OD) was measured at 570 nm. The difference between control and variable doses of proteases is determined through one way ANOVA test (Bonferroni multiple comparison test). *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01 and ***P < 0.001.

Total cellular content

The results of these studies related to protease isolated from chitinase enzyme containing Rapither AB as shown in Fig. 4. The results showed that protease at higher concentration showed reduction in total cellular content in virally infected human whole blood samples. On the other hand, virally infected sample showed enormous production of total cellular content.

Proliferation assay

The effect of protease using variable concentration on virally infected human whole blood samples and determined its effect on proliferation assay using MTT as shown in Fig. 5. The results showed that protease at higher concentration showed remarkable reduction in proliferation assay as compared to control.

DISCUSSION

As per the literature, chitinases producing organisms have been identified and isolated from various sources i.e. air, water, soil, marine water etc. [16]. In addition, chitinases also identified and isolated from the stomach of certain mammals including humans. As per its applications, chitinases are used as fungicides, bacteriocides, biopesticides, against mosquitoes etc. In the present study, numerous bacteria samples were reported and identified in soil samples and is able to produce various chitinases in order to supply various nutrients especially nitrogen and carbon. These chitinases were generally used for degrading chitin molecules and utilized as an energy source. One of the most dominant and prevalent bacteria i.e. *Serratia marcescens* that is responsible for producing chitinases and showed various immunopharmacological properties e.g. chitinases/chitinase-like proteins that played a crucial role in innate as well as adaptive immune responses [17, 18]. Although nonspecific type of immune stimulatory functions of chitin and its derivatives were reported and considered as potent immunoadjuvant candidate that enhances type 2 adaptive immune response. In this regard, we focused on chitinases especially its crude enzyme against Rapither AB in virally infected human whole blood samples.

From these soil samples, chitinase producers were isolated on colloidal chitin agar medium and its result was totally similar [19]. In addition, chitin acts as a sole carbon source for highest chitinase production [18, 19]. In this study, we isolate chitinase with protease activity containing Rapither AB and testing on virally infected human whole blood samples that will help us in order to understand its anti-viral properties. Firstly, estimated its total protein including amino acids content from chitinase colonies dissolved in PBS and results showed some enhancement at a very low concentration (i.e. 10 µl containing 5.345 mg/ml) using Tris HCl and ice cold acetone. After getting the protein content from chitinase colonies, centrifuging these samples and collect supernatant in the form of crude enzyme and further dissolved in similar volume of injection i.e. Rapither AB. For estimation of protease content using Folin Colins reagent and determined through Nanodrop method. In this study, we determined the interaction between protease and antigen (virally)-specific human whole blood that provides an important signals for the efficient activation or inhibition of T cell response. In order to determine its protease activity by means of proliferation and total cellular content in infected human whole blood samples. The results of these showed that protease at higher concentration showed remarkably decline in total cellular content and proliferation rate in infected lysed human whole blood samples.

These proteases are showed some potential or ability to reduce the burden of various infectious diseases. Recently, proteases derived from micro-organisms including medicinal plant products are the major source for drug development. Most of proteases derived from micro-organisms that are available or still under clinical trials [20]. In view of this, similar results were observed in case of protease extracted from chitinase crude enzyme containing Rapither AB and showed fascinating immunopharmacological property i.e. antimicrobial. Hopefully, this protease also involved in various applications especially for biotechnology. However the isolation and purification of proteases will assist us to recognize the mechanism of various disease models.

CONCLUSION

Immunological finding of proteases extracted from crude enzyme of chitinase containing Rapither AB was very interesting with respect to decline in proliferation rate and total cellular content in virally infected human whole blood samples. Further studies are required pertaining to isolation, characterization and elucidation of structures of these proteases.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

This work was carried out in collaboration between four authors. AG, MP and SS designed the study, wrote the protocol and interpreted the data where MP anchored the field study, gathered the initial data related to his M.Sc. Microbiology dissertation work under AG guidance and performed preliminary data analysis. AG, MP, SS and NP managed the literature searches whereas AG and MP produced the initial draft. The final manuscript has been read and approved by all authors.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no conflict of interests exists.

REFERENCES

1. Lenardon MD, Munro, Gow NAR. Chitin synthesis and fungal pathogenesis. *Curr Opin Microbiol.* 2010; 13: 416-423.
2. Synowiecki J, Al-Khateeb NA. Production, properties, and some new applications of chitin and its derivatives. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.* 2003; 43(2): 145-171.
3. Tharanathan RN, Kittur FS. Chitin - the undisputed biomolecule of great potential. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.* 2003; 43(1): 61-87.
4. Kurita K. Chitin and chitosan: functional biopolymers from marine crustaceans. *Marine Biotechnol.* 2006; 8(3): 203-226.
5. Krithika S, Chellaram C. Isolation, screening, and characterization of chitinase producing bacteria from marine wastes. *Int J Pharm Pharmac Sci.* 2016; 8(5): 34-36.
6. Bansode VB, Bajekal SS. Characterization of chitinases from microorganism from Lonar Lake. *Indian J Biotechnol.* 2006; 5(3): 357-363.
7. Rathore AS, Gupta RD. Chitinases from bacteria to human: properties, applications, and future perspectives. *Enzyme Res.* 2015; 791907.
8. Senol M, Nadaroglu H, Dikbas N, Kotan R. Purification of chitinase enzymes from *Bacillus subtilis* bacteria TV-125, investigation of kinetic properties and antifungal activity against *Fusarium culmorum*. *Ann Clin Microbiol Antimicrob.* 2014; 13: 35.
9. Gupta A, Chaphalkar SR. Current approaches and problems in malaria vaccine development. *Eur J Biol Res.* 2016; 6(1): 14-20.
10. Hartman TK, Rogerson SJ, Fischer PR. The impact of maternal malaria on newborns. *Ann Trop Paediatrics.* 2010; 30(4): 271-282.
11. Collins WE, Barnwell JW. *Plasmodium knowlesi*: finally being recognized. *J Infect Dis.* 2009; 199(8): 1107-1108.
12. Lyon RC, Taylor JS, Porter DA, Prasanna HR, Hussain AS. Stability profiles of drug products extended beyond labeled expiration dates. *J Pharmac Sci.* 2006; 95: 1549-1560.
13. Priya CS, Jagannathan N, Kalaichelvan PT. Production of chitinase by *Streptomyces hygroscopicus* vmch2 by optimisation of cultural conditions. *Int J Pharma Bio Sci.* 2011; 2(2): 210-219.
14. Gupta A, Shah AP, Chaphalkar SR. Immunopharmacological exploration of proteases from *Catharanthus roseus* on virally infected human whole blood. *J Dis Global Health.* 2016; 6(1): 36-42.

15. Gupta A, Chaphalkar SR. Analytical studies of protease extracted from *Azadirachta indica*. *World J Pharmac Res.* 2015; 4(11): 1391-1398.
16. Wang SL, Chang WT. Purification and characterization of two bifunctional chitinase by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* K-187 in a shrimp and crab shell powder medium. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 1997; 63: 380-386.
17. Hejazi A, Falkiner FR. *Serratia marcescens*. *J Med Microbiol.* 1997; 46(11): 903-912.
18. Krause R, Piening K, Ullman U. Inhibitory effects of various micro-organisms on the growth of *Helicobacter pylori*. *Lett Appl Microbiol.* 2005; 40: 81-86.
19. Mahmood ME. Production of chitinase from *Serratia marcescens* by using solid and liquid fermentation state and its role in biological treatment. Thesis MD, College of Science/ University of Baghdad, Iraq, 2007.
20. Gupta A, Shah AP, Chabukswar AR, Chaphalkar SR. Current necessity of proteases: overview. *J Biomed Pharmac Res.* 2016; 5(1): 52-64.